

Marketing Strategy Analysis of Boon Rawd Brewery Company

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Abstract—Boon Rawd Brewery is a beer company based in Thailand that has an exemplary image, both as a good employer and a well-managed company with a strong record of social responsibility. The most famous of the company's products is Singha beer. To study the company's marketing strategy, a case study analysis was conducted together with qualitative research methods. The study analyzed the marketing strategy of Boon Rawd Brewery before the liberalization of the liquor market in 2000. The company's marketing strategies consisted of the following: product line strategy, product development strategy, block channel strategy, media strategy, trade strategy, and consumer incentive strategy. Additionally, the company employed marketing mix strategy based on the 4Ps: product, price, promotion and place (of distribution).

Keywords—Beer, Boon Rawd Brewery Company, Marketing Strategy.

I. INTRODUCTION

BOON Rawd Brewery, founded by Phraya Bhirom Bhakdi, was the first company to establish a brewery in Thailand in 1933, with an initial registered capital in the amount of 600,000 baht. Its original production capacity, however, was only 20 million liters a year. The company has been in the beer business for 80 years, its main products being beer, soda, and drinking water, the aim being to meet consumer demand. The company improved and developed its products to meet the requisite standards in order to enhance consumer satisfaction. The company was also a distributor of Singha, Leo, Super Leo, and Mittweida beer.

II. OBJECTIVE

The main objective is to analyze the following: (1) The marketing objectives, (2) The marketing strategies, and (3) The marketing mix of Boon Rawd Brewery before the liberalization of the liquor market in 2000.

III. METHODOLOGY

Boon Rawd Brewery, which distributed beer (mainly Singha, Leo, Super Leo, Super Lion, and Mittweida), constituted the case study analyzed for the purposes of this research. The study used the qualitative method for gathering data from primary and secondary sources. The primary data was gathered from in-depth interviews with experts on the beer industry, while the secondary data was gathered from

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textbooks, journals, dissertations, newspapers, newsletters and seminars.

IV. FINDINGS

A. Marketing Objectives

The marketing objectives of the company were as follows: (1) To scramble the market share as much as possible in the standard, premium, and super premium segments of the market for Singha, Singha Gold, Singha Draft and Mittweida beer, (2) To increase the market share of Leo beer from 20% to 30% in 1999, (3) To gain market share for Super Leo beer amounting to at least 15% of the beer market, valued at 42,000 -43,000 million baht, or amounting to more than 700 million liters, (4) Super Leo beer was launched on December 28, 2000 with a sales target amounting to 50 million liters, equal to a 4% share of the beer market and valued at 40,000 million baht in the first year, with an advertising budget of 100 million baht.

The company's market share was more than 80%, but when Chang beer was launched in 1995 competition became fierce. However, the company's sales volume progressively diminished. The market share of Singha beer during 1995-1999 was 82%, 80%, 70%, 50% and 39% respectively. The company's sales totaled 364.9 million liters divided into the sales of Singha beer at 60.96%, Leo beer at 27.85% and so on. The sales volumes for 2000 (January - October) were as follows:

TABLE I
SALES VOLUME OF BOON RAWD BREWERY COMPANY, 2000 (JANUARY-OCTOBER)

Brand	Liter	Percent
Singha	222,416,379.21	60.96
Leo	101,615,426.24	27.85
Super Leo	34,021,542.24	9.32
Mittweida	2,514,419.28	0.69
Singha Gold	2,395,511.64	0.66
Singha Draft	1,919,887.20	0.53
Total	364,883,165.81	100

Source: Department of Excise, Ministry of Finance

TABLE II
SALE SHARE OF CHANG, SINGHA, LEO AND SUPER LEO BEER (JANUARY-OCTOBER 2000)

Brand	Sales Volume (Million Liters)	Sales Volume (Million Liters)
Chang	559.90	559.90
Singha	136.39	
Leo	113.72	270.69
Super Leo	20.58	

In relation to its three brands, the sales volume of the company was only 270.69 million liters, which was below 50% of that of Chang beer. This was caused by the following: (1) The state of the Thai economy was stagnant, (2) Consumers turned to drinking cheaper beers, (3) Although there was a high degree of brand loyalty regarding Singha beer, people still resorted to drinking Chang, which was cheaper, due to the economic slowdown.

Leo and Super Leo beer were launched in 1998 in direct competitor to Chang beer. However, Leo beer's success was achieved by scrambling the market share by more than 20%. Most of this was seized from Singha's market share and not from that of Chang. Super Leo beer's market share stood at 2-3%. Chang beer's market share still continued to increase by selling local liquor bundled with Chang beer.

However, it was impossible to further reduce the retail price of Super Lion beer, which was close to Leo beer, namely, 370 baht per crate or approximately 30 - 35 baht per bottle. The bigger proportion of Chang beer sold together with local liquor boosted Chang's sales by a great deal. The company filed a complaint, requesting fair treatment and an end to the strategy of selling local liquor together with Chang beer. The complaint was filed in stages. Finally, it was judged by a sub-committee dealing with trade competition, the Ministry of Commerce, that selling local liquor together with Chang beer was not illegal. It was one of the sales procedures which was not appropriate.

B. Marketing Strategy

Development of a marketing orientation, difficult thought this can be in many organizations, is only one side of the coin in improving the marketing effectiveness of an organization. Marketing strategy specifies a target market and a related marketing mix [4]. Marketing strategy is concerned with finding sustainable ways for organizations to complete in a continuously changing world. The company's marketing strategies were as follows:

1. Product Line Strategy

A product line is a group of products that are closely related because they perform a similar function, are sold to the same customer groups, are marketed through the same channels, or fall within a given price range. Product line managers need to know the sales and profits of each item in their line in order to determine which items to build, maintain, harvest, or divest. They also need to understand each product's market profile [3].

The company produced new beers to compete in every segment for the following purposes: (1) Selling for competition, (2) Scrambling for market share and insertion into the marketing space, (3) The liquidity in the laying down of market policy and cooperation with one's business allies, (4) Having an increased amount of products to serve the demand for Singha Draft beer with a mild taste to attract customers who like its smooth taste.

TABLE III
 PRODUCT LINE OF BOON RAWD BREWERY COMPANY

Brand	Type	Fighting Brand	Date of Distribution
Singha Gold	Premium	Kloster	1985
Leo	Standard	Chang	24 June 1998
Super Leo	Standard	Change	4 April 1999 23 December 1999 (no ceased producing)
Mittweida	Super Premium	Brew Max	28 October 1999
Super Lion	Standard	Chang	2000

2. Product Development Strategy

After successfully completing the business analysis stage, product planning moves to development and testing [1]. In 1998, the company received the certificate of universal standard quality, or ISO 9002, from S.G.S. (Thailand). In December 1985, the company began to wade into the market by developing a new beer named "Singha Gold", which was a kind of beer that had a low alcoholic content of about 3.5%, similar to that of a light beer. Thus, it was a kind of beer, though its taste was lighter than that of both Singha and Kloster. Consequently, Singha Gold beer was positioned as a beer for the new generation.

3. Block Channel Strategy

Singha traders throughout the country were composed of those from the upper and lower northern parts of the country, Bangkok traders, suburban traders, eastern traders, traders from the upper and lower central parts of the country, traders from the upper and lower Northeastern part of Thailand and traders from the upper and lower southern part. The duty and role of the 11 Singha traders could be described as follows: (1) Each trader had a list of his customers' names to prevent them from scrambling for customers, with the exception of newly emergent customers, (2) To seek new customers instead of waiting, (3) Selling competitors' products including soda, drinking water and beer, was forbidden, (4) In order to get rid of overlapping where sales lines were concerned and prevent distributors from undercutting one another, the parent company (Boon Rawd Brewery Company) established the same sales prices. Meetings would be held by the syndicates on a monthly basis. In cases involving any violation of the regulations, the individual's right to be an agent would be revoked and the vacancy would not be filled. Accordingly, all the agents did their best to maintain their status to their fullest capacity.

4. Media Strategy

Advertising can be used to build up a long-term image for a product [3]. Advertising was emphasized by the company as a key factor in promoting its products and in stressing value, the unique identity of Thai art, culture and traditions, sports, and excellence in society. Over several years in the past, it had been recognized that the advertising of Singha beer was outstanding, standardized, and worthy in terms of its highlighting of art and culture, as well as providing useful knowledge.

5. Trade Strategy

Trade promotion can persuade the retailer or wholesaler to carry more units than normal. The company will offer volume allowances to get the trade to carry more in their warehouses and stores. The company believed that the trade will work harder when they load the company's product [3]. To increase sales volume, the company used trade strategies and incentives for sellers and arranged for promotional campaigns by Singha agents countrywide to mark the occasion of its 60th anniversary (in 1993). The purpose was to encourage agents to be enthusiastic, to accelerate the release of beers for distribution as much as possible, and to select agents who achieved their targeted sales volume. The sales volume of each syndicate was not less than 100 million baht. Singha traders who proved outstanding were selected to conduct on-site studies and to pay a visit to the October Festival in Munich, Germany, September 22 – 29, 1993.

6. Consumer Incentive Strategy

Programs related to lucky draws of entries found under the bottle caps of Singha beer and various other products produced by the company were held several times, while sports marketing was promoted to encourage public participation in social activities with massive numbers of people in attendance. The company sponsored a country road circuit fair (an annual racing fair), made the arrangements for a marathon relay race or "Green relay marathon", and joined in the arrangement of Singha Draught festivals at designated outlets at the end of every year and so forth, was some of the company's other promotional activities.

C. Marketing Mix Strategy

Firms seek a competitive advantage and synergy, planning a well-integrated program of marketing-mix elements (primarily the 4P's of product, price, promotion, and place of distribution) tailored to the needs and wants of customers in the target segments [6]. The marketing mix of the company was as follows:

1. Product Strategy

Though price, promotion, and distribution are also effective, the product normally figures most importantly in strategy because (1) Better products are basic to winning and keeping market share and (2) Growth is a normal objective of enterprise [5]. Singha was a beer with differences in alcoholic content. There were three forms: (1) Singha beer contained 4.9% alcohol by volume and was called lager beer (2) Singha Gold Light, containing 4% alcohol called light beer, (3) Singha Draught, containing 3.9% alcohol called draught beer.

In 1998, the company received a certificate for universal standard quality, or ISO 9002, from S.G.S. (Thailand) company. This enabled Singha to be recognized as a beer of universal standard and launch into exporting to foreign countries. Also, the product line strategy was used by the company to ensure that there was a full inventory of its products for each segment of the market.

The quality and image of the Singha brand was to be maintained by stressing its image as a Thai product, the kind

of beer that Thai people preferred to drink. This allowed Singha beer to cultivate a high degree of brand loyalty, while at the same time stressing its image of appealing to a new generation with its Singha Gold beer.

The product's quality was thoroughly improved by the company; in 1985, for instance, a new tasting beer named Singha Gold beer was produced. It was a beer with a low alcoholic content of 3.5%, so it was called a light beer. In addition, the packaging of Super Leo beer was greatly improved in April 2000 by replacing the old label with a new one which highlighted the word "Super" (by using bigger letters) while de-emphasizing the word "Leo" (by using smaller letters).

TABLE IV
 TYPES OF PRODUCTS PRODUCED BY BOON RAWD BREWERY COMPANY

Type of Products	Brand
Premium (Lager Beer)	Singha Beer
Premium (Light Beer)	Singha Gold
Fresh Beer	Singha Draft Can
Standard	Leo
Standard	Super Leo
Standard	Super Lion
Super Premium	Mittweida

Singha was a leading beer whose appearance was constantly being improved. It was regarded as one more step in its development, namely its taste was still maintained, but its packaging was improved by wrapping foil on the bottle, substituting the white bottle neck and a white paper box with a light brown one for the following reasons: (1) It was an adjustment to the positioning of Singha beer becoming a universal or an international beer, (2) Being a brand in competition with a variety of foreign brands, and (3) Being able to dispatch Singha beer into foreign markets in larger quantities.

The packaging and quality of Singha Gold beer were developed in a thorough manner. The company, therefore, produced canned Singha Gold beer with its distinctive Stay on Tap (SOT) to modernize its product like foreign beers. Both canned Singha and canned Singha Gold, sold at a fixed price, began distribution on May 28, 1993 with an emphasis on conservation of the environment.

In 1993, a new canned beer was produced along the lines of the Stay on Tap (SOT) to be used with Singha Gold beer. The advantages were as follows: (1) It helped to conserve the environment and to allow the can to be recycled; (2) It was a package belonging to the modern era, of a type in popular use.

2. Price Strategy

Companies set their price strategies to achieve several objectives. They might price for results (sales, market share, profit), for market penetration or position, or for certain other functions. The choice of a price strategy depends on how management has decided to price its good or service relative to the competition [1].

It was still desirable for the company to maintain its price due to the economic crisis that beset Thailand in the middle of

1997, which resulted in the following: (1) Consumer behavior changed from drinking expensive beers to drinking cheaper ones due to the diminishing purchasing power of consumers caused by a reduction in their salaries or the laying-off of large numbers of employees, (2) Since its competitor produced Chang beer (at a cheap price) to sell in competition with it, the company was thus forced to produce new beers such as Leo, Super Leo and Super Lion to be sold at cheaper prices in competition with Chang beer.

There was no discount for company agents even though its products were bought in large quantities. The price to the agents was the same for everybody, but agents had to provide vehicles to pick up the items from the company by themselves and provide payment in cash. Products could be received at any time and when the products had nearly run out, new supplies could be picked up upon request.

3. Promotional Strategy

Marketing management should develop an integrated promotion strategy. To communicate with and influence customers, several promotion tools are available. Advertising is usually the most visible component of promotion, but it is not the only one. The company coordinated the roles of the various promotion components, selecting strategies for advertising, personal sales, sales promotion, and public relations. Nevertheless, these communications may influence a firm's target audience [7].

The company's promotional objectives were as follows: (1) To stimulate sales volume and increase market share, (2) To serve as the principal policy of the company to participate in conducting activities with agents and shops, (3) To create customer brand awareness and to keep products in the consciousness of consumers. The company's marketing practice was undertaken to achieve the following: (1) Maintain market share, (2) Increase sales volume. The promotional strategy adopted by each brand was as follows:

1. Singha. The marketing policy, including the promotion of Singha beer, was undertaken consecutively to maintain market share and increase sales volume by means of the following: (1) Making multi-vision slides in large dimensions with a budget of approximately 1 million baht, with the emphasis on Chiang Rai province because it was an area that had maintained its culture, both past and present and was particularly impressive, especially when coupled with a beer industry of good quality. Products in the Kaladiner fair were exhibited to mark the occasion of the company's 25th anniversary at the Viphavadee Ballroom in the Central Plaza Hotel, the event being televised countrywide via Channel 7, (2) The company supported promotional activities jointly with Singha agents throughout the country, presenting rewards to those agents who achieved the top sales volume for each syndicate of not less than 100 million baht. The winners got to travel to conduct on-site studies and visit the October Festival at Munich in Germany during September 22–29, 1993, (3) The company arranged promotions in a new style that encouraged consumers to have fun participating in programs advertising Singha beer by sending in Singha beer crown caps for a lucky

draw lots to name a movie star who drank beer in the motion picture *Entrapment*.

A screening of the motion picture "*Entrapment*" was arranged in collaboration with the Twenty Century Fox Thailand Company, together with a campaign that involved guessing the name of a global movie star who drank Singha beer in the movie, with prizes worth a total value of more than 200,000 baht. Participants were asked to send in their answers by using coupons from newspapers or by writing on postcards or on movie tickets along with one crown cap of Singha beer. The participants had to fill in their name and address at the lucky draw receptacles in front of cinema foyers or post them to the company.

2. Singha Gold. Singha Gold beer was first produced as a premium beer in 1985; the purpose was to disrupt the growth of Kloster. Singha Gold had a total sales volume valued at approximately 3-4% of the company's entire income. Products were developed and promotions were held on a continuous basis to increase sales volume and to encourage consumers to drink Singha Gold beer.

In 1991, Singha Gold beer managed to be a key sponsor for a tournament entitled "Gold Light Beer Country Road Circuit 1991," comprising 5 fields as shown below:

TABLE V
 COUNTRY ROAD CIRCUIT FAIR

Location	Distance (kms.)	Date of Tournament
Phitsanulok	16	Feb 24, 1991
Phuket	25	May 5, 1991
Kwae River	Mini marathon	Sept. 15, 1991
Mae Sot	25	July 20, 1991
Lanna	25	Dec. 22, 1991

The marketing strategy for Singha Gold beer was carried out consecutively to familiarize customers country-wide with the product and to increase consumption. Sport was one public activity that brought the company closer to its customers by collaborating with work action, a strange style of running was once arranged by the company in the form of a relay race comprising of teams with eight persons in each with the average distance run by each person per day being 12.5 kms. The event was named "Singha Gold Light Earth Relay Marathon - Overcoming Green Mountain" which became (1) A deviation from the normal marathon race, offering an extra challenge and (2) An attraction for tourists, both Thais and foreigners alike, who loved running coupled with offers to sell Singha Gold beer to the spectators. The route for this tournament, which took place on October 23 and 24, 1992, was through / over a mountain, Highway # 1095 which connected Chiang Mai and Mae Hong Son provinces, covering a distance of 100 kms a day.

3. Singha Draft. In order to make Singha Draft beer more attractive, with a broader appeal, including the capacity to provide other kinds of beer for distribution jointly, while focusing on the accelerated release of beers onto the market, coupled with the advertising of Singha beer at various festivals in a comprehensive manner. On April 1, 1990, the first vehicle from Germany was used by the company as a mobile

advertising media for distribution at festivals countrywide. The main objective was to serve draft, bottled, and canned beer to customers directly at different festivals, as in the following examples:

TABLE VI
SINGHA DRAFT BEER PROMOTION STRATEGY

Period of Time	Location
April 1, 1990	Kite fair at Pattaya , Cholburi province
April 25 – May 1, 1990	Bike Fair at Amporn Garden, Bangkok
Oct. – Dec. 1997	Beer Gardens or Draft Beer Parks were arranged at various locations such as the World Trade Centre, Siam Discovery, and Park Plaza.
Nov. – Feb. 1999	Singha Draft Festivals were held at (1) Ambassador Hotel, (2) SOKO Trade Centre and (3) Time square, Asoke–Dindaeng Road.

TABLE VII
NUMBER OF BEER GARDENS AMONG BRANDS

Brand	Number of Beer Gardens
Singha	120
Carlsberg	20
Heineken	20
Kloster	5

Advertising: The objectives were as follows: (1) It was regarded as a key factor in sales promotion, (2) It concentrated on the distribution of value and the unique identity of eminent Thai arts and culture, while at the same time providing useful knowledge, (3) It made repeat messages pertaining to its brands to keep them in consumers' memories, (4) Encouraged consumers to increase their number of purchases, and (5) Weighed the importance of advertising to approach specific target groups.

TABLE IX
SINGHA BEER'S ADVERTISING BUDGET FOR ALL MEDIA (THOUSAND BAHT)

Year	TV	Radio	Press	Magazines	Outdoors	Cinema	Total
1989	47,426 (82.01%)	3,737 (6.46%)	2,304 (3.98%)	3,402 (5.88%)	480 (0.83%)	480 (0.83%)	57,829 (100%)
1990	61,824 (79.69%)	7,245 (9.34%)	1,667 (2.15%)	3,691 (4.76%)	576 (0.74%)	2,574 (3.32%)	77,577 (100%)
1991	62,413 (79.34%)	8,647 (10.99%)	1,206 (1.53%)	2,912 (3.70%)	576 (0.73%)	2,911 (3.70%)	78,665 (100%)
1992	73,927 (77.05%)	11,229 (11.70%)	1,858 (1.94%)	4,563 (4.76%)	-	4,364 (4.55%)	95,941 (100%)
1993	85,497 (71.46%)	12,914 (10.79%)	9,994 (8.35%)	5,065 (4.23%)	1,926 (1.61%)	4,249 (3.55%)	119,645 (100%)
1994	120,557 (81.15%)	12,674 (8.53%)	2,990 (2.01%)	5,506 (3.71%)	5,155 (3.47%)	1,687 (1.14%)	148,569 (100%)
1995	165,858 (74.85%)	36,823 (16.62%)	7,051 (3.18%)	4,101 (1.85%)	6,764 (3.05%)	990 (0.45%)	221,587 (100%)
1996	266,183 (75.57%)	58,258 (16.54%)	4,526 (1.28%)	6,367 (1.81%)	15,616 (4.43%)	1,294 (0.37%)	352,244 (100%)
1997	233,026 (68.33%)	80,275 (23.54%)	3,584 (1.05%)	6,655 (1.95%)	16,278 (4.77%)	1,233 (0.36%)	341,051 (100%)
1998	243,991 (81.19%)	35,543 (11.83%)	5,645 (1.88%)	5,608 (1.87%)	9,432 (3.14%)	300 (0.10%)	300,519 (100%)
1999	343,319 (87.61%)	22,639 (5.78%)	13,187 (3.37%)	6,428 (1.64%)	1,200 (0.31%)	5,089 (1.30%)	391,862 (100%)
2000	149,780 (91.68%)	3,331 (2.04%)	2,257 (1.58%)	2,257 (1.58%)	560 (0.34%)	4,878 (2.99%)	163,381 (100%)

Source: Media Data Resources Company

4. Leo: The strategy for promoting Leo beer could be described as follows:

With regards to the purpose of penetrating the market as fast as possible, the company, in cooperation with 300 agents, arranged a special campaign during the first two months (July–August 1998) by distributing 3 bottles of beer and then giving one extra bottle as a free gift – all within the price of 100 baht. Agents provided full cooperation by agreeing to reduce their profit and to sell within the price limit of 36 baht a bottle after the campaign period was over.

Through advertising, the company was presented via virtually every type of media such as television, radio, cinema, magazines, newspapers and other media, thus making it accessible to audiences and consumers in a broad and effective manner.

The advertisement for each brand was selected by the companies to ensure there was a clear differentiation with regard to each product as shown in Table VIII.

TABLE VIII
ADVERTISING OF BOON RAWD BREWERY COMPANY

Brand	Advertising Companies
Singha beer , Singha Soda and Singha Drinking Water	Ogilvy & Mather Company
Singha Gold beer	Leo Burnett Company
Canned Singha and Singha Gold	Winbeck & Odds Company

Singha: Advertising was carried out in the form of a soft sell and concentrated on creating an image of being a 100 percent Thai beer. Most consumers felt that Singha beer took part in the strengthening of Thai society, possessing the properties both of being Thai and having a good taste. The budget for advertising was allocated by the company to every kind of media, such as television, radio, newspapers, magazines, outdoor and indoor cinema, with a strong emphasis on television due to its easy access to customers. The requirement was to make a brand repeat, so the medium of television was used to create both image and sound. The advertising budget for Singha beer, classified according to various types of media, is shown in Table IX.

Promotional activities for Leo beer were held at a fair titled "Great Fun Celebration of Leo" or Leo Fun Fest beginning in April through to December 1999 (a total of 8 consecutive months) with an investment budget of 50 million baht, the fair being held in collaboration with a total of 330 Singha agents countrywide. The objective of the fair arrangement was to conduct public relations for Leo to increase its current market share from 20–23% to approximately 30% within 1999 (it was a mutual sales activity undertaken by Leo and Super Leo beer).

Several times, promotional activities were arranged in conjunction with Leo and Super Leo beer, such as the following: (1) The lucky draw program using crown caps for Leo and Super Leo beer, (2) Arranging concert (music marketing) programs countrywide (from the end of 1999 to the first quarter of 2000) - a total of 17 concerts, (3) Arranging the 2nd music program of Leo and Super Leo beer, which also involved in lucky draws using crown caps in the same manner, but also giving away a bottle of beer as an extra gift.

From August 2000 onward, the promotional activities of Leo and Super Leo beer were separated from each other in a clear-cut manner because in the past they had caused customers some confusion.

Advertising: The advertising budget for the first year was around 70 million baht (with 30 million baht being used in the

first three months). Young people were used as presenters to reach out to the new generation. It was a kind of motion-picture that focused on natural surroundings and proper preservation. The advertising motion-picture constituted a complete deviation from the norm, which included plots with dialogues, gags and a country-style marriage ceremony, the message being that this beer was appropriate for every type of joyous occasion.

Regarding the advertising of Leo beer, media via television, radio, newspapers and magazines were used which was mostly concentrated on advertising via television especially during Leo beer's launching period in order to compete with Chang beer. The advertising budgets for Leo according to various media are shown in Table X.

TABLE X
 LEO BEER'S ADVERTISING BUDGET FOR ALL MEDIA (THOUSAND BAHT)

Year	TV	Radio	Press	Magazines	Outdoors	Cinema	Total
1998	125,155 (96.19%)	1,155 (0.89%)	3,155 (2.42%)	648 (0.50%)	-	-	130,113 (100%)
1999	228,058 (92.35%)	4,183 (1.69%)	12,112 (4.90%)	2,606 (1.06%)	-	-	246,959 (100%)
2000	162,365 (90.02%)	9,308 (5.16%)	8,063 (4.47%)	624 (0.35%)	-	-	180,360 (100%)

Source: Media Data Resources Company

5. Super Leo: Joint promotion activities undertaken between Leo and Super Leo beer were as follows: (1) A lucky draw program using crown caps of Leo and Super Leo beer was held in conjunction with beer traders under the title "Open one bottle and get one more bottle free" commencing from April 7, 2000 to the end of the month. The condition was that the lucky person that opened the plastic under a crown cap and found the picture of a leopard, could exchange it for a new bottle of Leo beer worth 35 – 37 baht a bottle for the price of 5 baht instead. If the words "lucky draw" were specified, it could be sent in to draw lots for five dozen beers, comprising 500 prizes in all using a total budget of 90 million baht, (2) It was a program for drawing lots under crown caps of Leo and Super Leo beer with a bottle of beer as an extra gift. It consisted of programs for general consumers that were stimulated by crown caps of Leo and Super Leo beer. A lucky person could cast lots for four automobiles -- a Toyota Sport Rider, a Tiger Truck, and gold in the form of 300 necklaces. In a joint activity with Seven-Eleven stores, crown caps valued at 5 baht could be exchanged for any item in the joint product group except for alcohol, (3) Music marketing and concerts were held countrywide from late 1999 to March 2000.

After the completion of the lucky draw program, which was won by Leo beer for the second time (August 2000), the promotional activities of Leo and Super Leo beer were separated from each other due to the confusion it caused for consumers. It was desirable to let consumers remember the

beers in a more effective manner; therefore a kind of alcoholic beer was added. An increase in its competitive approach and clear-cut advertising enabled Super Leo beer to increase its sales.

6. Mittweida: The promotional strategies were as follows: (1) Promotions at places of entertainment, pubs, bars, or at concert points, (2) An advertising budget of 50 million baht, (3) Producing advertising brochures. The media for advertising Mittweida beer were television, radio, newspapers, magazines and outdoor postings, although in point of fact, most of the advertising was done through television. The advertising budget for Mittweida beer was classified according to the various media it employed, as shown in Table XI.

Promotional strategies during the slowdown in the economy were conducted by a reduction in expenses in the following respects: (1) Cutting the budget related to advertising and public relations by about 25% (in 1997, for example, it was formally established in the amount of 500 million baht, and subsequently reduced to 37.5 million baht), (2) Reducing the cost related to the transportation of various agents by increasing transportation in the night time to solve the problem of traffic jams and to increase the efficiency of the market, (3) An on-line computer system was used to link the company and its various agents countrywide to enable the communication of marketing information and to make the ordering of beers more rapid.

TABLE XI
 MITTWEIDA BEER'S ADVERTISING BUDGET FOR ALL MEDIA (THOUSAND BAHT)

Year	TV	Radio	Press	Magazines	Outdoors	Cinema	Total
1999	74,055 (83.28%)	7,716 (8.68%)	3,307 (3.72%)	600 (0.67%)	420 (0.47%)	2,827 (3.18%)	88,925 (100%)
2000	93,941 (79.87%)	9,098 (7.74%)	1,635 (1.39%)	4,245 (3.61%)	2,280 (1.94%)	6,409 (5.40%)	117,608 (100%)

Source: Media Data Resources Company

7. Super Lion. Its promotional strategy was conducted by means of advertising, especially on television. The advertising

of Super Lion beer is classified below by the media it employed, as shown in Table XII.

TABLE XII
 SUPER LION BEER'S ADVERTISING BUDGET FOR ALL MEDIA

Year	TV	Radio	Press	Magazine	Outdoor	Cinema	Total
2000	5,781		1,880				7,661
	(75.46%)		(24.54%)				(100%)

Source: Media Data Resource Company

4. Place (of Distribution) Strategy

Channel strategy consists of interrelated decisions in four areas: the type of channel, distribution intensity, channel design, and channel management. These decisions include selecting the type of channel arrangement, determining the desired intensity of distribution, designing the channel configuration, and managing the channel on an ongoing basis [2].

According to the distribution structure of Singha beer, traders would be organized by the company to act as distributors to department stores, supermarkets, etc., using vehicles that belonged to the company and carrying products from the company to distribution areas directly. Distribution via agents was consisted of the following: (1) Agents in the Bangkok Metropolitan region which would be divided into the Bangkok region and its suburban areas and (2) Provincial agents and agents in Bangkok Metropolis who were required to pick up products directly from the company in order to distribute them to sub-agents for further distribution to retail shops.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The company applies both marketing strategy and marketing mix. The company's marketing strategies consisted of product line strategy, product development strategy, block channel strategy, media strategy, trade strategy, and consumer incentive strategy. On the other hand, marketing mix or the 4P's strategy was used by the company as follows:

Product Strategy: (1) Every product segment was produced in response to customer demand in various levels of income, (2) With regards to product development strategy; the brewery was improved in 1998 to the point where a certificate of quality, ISO 9002, was obtained. In 1998, plans were underway to improve the quality of the company's products in accordance with universal standards, including the ability to maintain the quality of the taste and the image of Singha beer by stressing the fact that it was a Thai beer that Thai people had preferred to drink for 67 years (in 2000) which gave Singha beer a high degree of brand loyalty, (3) Regarding the company's packaging strategy, modern technology was introduced by the company to make "Stay on Tap" products on October 31, 1990. a move that took environmental conservation and social demands into due consideration. It was a marketing idea that took society into account in the sense that benefits would be provided by the firm and returned to the society. Environmental pollution was a matter of concern to the firm; it was necessary, therefore, that

equilibrium is reached in the long term between a response to market demand and social welfare. The societal marketing concept would be concentrated on social conditions by upgrading the welfare of the people and improving the way of life in society by participating in the overall conservation of the environment as well.

Price strategy: Many new producers entered the market, and many brands emerged, such as Heineken, Carlsberg and Chang beer. Because of the Thai economic crisis of 1997, consumers' purchasing power decreased, which prompted them to turn to drinking less expensive beer, such as Chang. New beers were produced, such as Leo, Super Leo and Super Lion, which were cheap in order to respond to low-income consumers and to compete with Chang beer.

Promotion strategy: Media strategy, trade strategy, and consumer incentive strategy were used in order to create products of good quality in response to the market.

Place (of distribution) strategy: Since market share was achieved, with sales volume in the top rank of the market, block channel strategy was used and new agents were added when three breweries entered the already competitive market.

The year 2000 was regarded as the year when the fight to scramble market share was fiercer than in any other period and it seemed that each group attempted to apply every form of strategy to win the fight.

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